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**MANAGEMENT OF SUPERVISORS MADRASAH IN QUALITY
IMPROVEMENT MADRASAH ALIYAH IN JAMBI PROVINCE
(ANALYSIS OF PAI SUBJECT SUPERVISORS AT MADRASAH ALIYAH)**

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Abstract

Good supervision will create the professionalism of teachers in learning so as to produce good learning achievements and then produce good graduate competencies. The main questions in this dissertation research are: why is the management of supervisors in improving the quality of madrasah education at MAN / MAS Jambi City, Muaro Jambi District, East Tanjung Jabung Regency and Kerinci District?

This study uses descriptive qualitative research methods with sampling techniques carried out by purposive sampling. The subjects of this study were the Aliyah Madrasah Supervisor as the key informant, while the Head of the Madrasah Education Division, the City / District Ministry of Religion, the Head of the Aliyah Madrasah, and the teacher as the informant. Furthermore, the technique of collecting data using interviews, observations and documentation studies. Data analysis using flow data analysis models include: data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing.

The results of this study found that first, the management of supervisors in Madrasah Aliyah has not been done optimally. Madrasah Aliyah supervisors have not yet made detailed monitoring plans based on their time period or period of work. Second, the internal factors that have not been optimal for Islamic Education supervisors in improving the quality of education in Aliyah Madrasah are as follows: 1) Lack of supervisory competence, 2) Low supervisory resources, 3) Lack of supervisory motivation, 4) Lack of supervisory commitment. While external factors have not been optimal, supervisors in improving the quality of Aliyah Madrasah are as follows: 1) Supervisory recruitment. 2) Effect of government policy. 3) Lack of support from the Ministry of Religion. Third, the efforts of Aliyah Madrasah supervisors in improving the quality of education are: 1) Enhancing supervisory abilities. 2) Supervision of supervisor performance, 3) Support from the Ministry of Religion. Fourth, models of supervisors who supervise the madrasa.

The implication of this research is that the management of supervisors in improving the quality of the Aliyah Madrasah in Jambi Province is reviewed through the application of management functions carried out by the Head of the Ministry of Religion Office, starting from the planning process to the work assessment. The results of this study are recommended to various parties as follows: first, it is expected that the Provincial Ministry of Religion Office as a competent party to

supervise the performance of the Aliyah Madrasah supervisors, secondly, it is expected that the head of madrasah proactively assists supervisors in supervising teachers in Madrasah , thirdly the community is demanded cooperation with supervisors in improving the quality of madrasa teachers.

Keywords: Management; Supervision and Quality of Madrasah.

Cite This Article: Khairinal, Adrianus Chatib, and Dailami Julis. (2019). “MANAGEMENT OF SUPERVISORS MADRASAH IN QUALITY IMPROVEMENT MADRASAH ALIYAH IN JAMBI PROVINCE (ANALYSIS OF PAI SUBJECT SUPERVISORS AT MADRASAH ALIYAH).” *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 7(7), 370-380. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364462>.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Madrasah supervisors conduct overall assessment and guidance on the implementation of education in the Madrasah concerned both in technical education and administration. The supervisor must also be able to evaluate the direction to the teachers in relation to improving their abilities in the learning process. The supervisors are also required to provide guidance and explanation of what, why and how to carry out the functions and tasks that must be performed by the teachers, especially with regard to the policies given in dealing with various possible problems that will be faced in the learning process.

11 Kabupaten / Kota in Jambi Province there are many Aliyah Madrasah, and those taken as the place of research are Aliyah Madrasah in Jambi City, Muaro Jambi Regency, East Tanjung Jabung Regency, and Kerinci Regency. The reasons are: 1). Aliyah Madrasah as a secondary education institution has the same position as other public education institutions, but the institution is less attractive to the Islamic community to send their children to school. 2). Madrasah Aliyah as an Islamic education institution has a dual role for students, which in addition to providing general knowledge also provides knowledge about religion. 3). Aliyah Madrasah has a madrasa head and teachers who are partially incompatible with educational qualifications, allegedly as a cause of declining education quality. 4). Aliyah Madrasah generally have honorary teachers, so that those who are civil servants do not commit to their basic teaching tasks. 5). Few Madrasah Aliyah graduates are accepted into superior universities.

Through preliminary observations, researchers looked at many factors of management of supervision which became a benchmark for the low development and quality improvement of madrasa education institutions. Among these factors are (1) Weak recruitment system, (2) Low bureaucratic attention to supervision, (3) main tasks are not in accordance with the function of supervision, (4) Inadequate infrastructure facilities, (5) There are some supervisors who are very low knowledge about supervision so that supervisors are reluctant to come to school, (6) The mechanism of supervision / supervision is poorly understood.

In the cultural aspect, there are obstacles, among others: First, policy makers about education and implementers in the field have not thought about developing a quality culture in education. If observed, the quality of education requested by customers actually lies in the quality of teaching and learning interactions between students and teachers. Second, cultural values of social interaction that are less positive, are brought about in functional and professional interactions between supervisors, principals and teachers, making the supervisors or principals unwilling to "go too far" in the teacher's area. Third, paternalistic culture, makes teachers not open and does not build professional relationships that are familiar with school principals and supervisors.

Researchers have conducted a grandtour at the Jambi City Islamic Senior High School (MA), Muaro Jambi District, East Tanjung Jabung Regency, and Kerinci Regency. We found various weaknesses regarding the management of supervisors for improving the quality of Madrasah that have not been optimally implemented as follows:

- 1) Madrasah Aliyah supervisors are appointed not in accordance with applicable laws and regulations, where MA supervisors are appointed from Administrative staff and Islamic Madrasah teachers.
- 2) The appointment of Madrasah Aliyah supervisors is not done with good recruitment. Supervisors appointed by the head of the Office of the Ministry of Religion are not subjected to a supervisory test but those appointed are employees who have almost expired.
- 3) MA supervisors do not have good competence. Where the supervisor does not guide the teacher in determining the appropriate educational goals, based on standards of competence and basic competencies in the process of learning activities in the classroom.
- 4) Fostering supervisors as an effort to improve learning activities at the Supreme Court has not been carried out optimally, so that supervisors do not have the expertise to develop supervisory programs. This is because supervisors rarely attend supervisory education and training, workshops and seminars.
- 5) The supervisor does not provide feedback (feedback) to the teacher who has been supervised. This feedback will be useful for the teacher to adjust, look back, and reinterpret problems and challenges in conducting learning activities in the classroom. The supervision that has been carried out by the Aliyah Madrasah supervisor is to perfect the teacher's understanding and knowledge in learning activities.
- 6) For supervisors MA in general subjects is very minimal, usually the many who become supervisors come from religious education qualifications so that in conducting supervision of teachers general lessons are not carried out optimally.

Seeing the phenomenon of the Jambi City MA supervisor, Muaro Jambi Regency, East Tanjung Jabung Regency, and Kerinci Regency which occurred as described above, certainly could cause the quality of Madrasah education to be neglected. If the Madrasah supervisor human resources in Jambi Province show this, of course it also affects the quality of teachers in the learning activities carried out. Among other things, the implementation of teaching preparation tools was neglected, even more than 8 basic teaching skills were not understood by the teacher. If the implementation of learning is not quality, it certainly affects the quality of students and ultimately affects the quality of education as a whole. One of the main tasks in improving the quality of Madrasah education is through the field of supervision.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Concept of Supervisor Management

Management is an activity to change things to become good and have high values from the original condition. In other words, management can be interpreted as an effort to do something to be more suitable and better suited to the desired needs so that it will be more useful. In other words the purpose of management in this study is a series of processes or activities which include planning, implementation, and evaluation of the supervision carried out by supervisors in improving the quality of Madrasah . The explanation of management in this study consists of the planning section, then the implementation, and then the evaluation carried out by the supervisor in conducting supervision of Madrasah to improve the quality of Madrasah . Achieving these set goals must go through various activities by implementing management functions which include planning, implementation and assessment processes.

Seeing how the management efforts of supervisors in improving the quality of Islamic religious schools in Jambi Province will be assessed through the application of management functions carried out by the Head of the Ministry of Religion Office, starting from the planning process that begins with the process of recruitment, training, guidance and work evaluation.

The school supervision program is a guideline for school supervisors in carrying out their main tasks and functions. The supervision program should be prepared in line with the vision, mission and goals of education in the target schools. The program prepared is directed at the professional services of school supervisors in order to improve the quality of education in schools. To realize this, there are several principles that need to be considered in the preparation of school supervision programs, including:

- 1) School supervision activities are developed on the basis of the results of supervision in the previous year. This shows that school supervision must be carried out continuously. In this case the principle of continuous quality improvement is applied (continuous quality improvement). Even though there is a change of supervisor, the new school supervisor must pay close attention to what has been done and achieved by the previous supervisor.
- 2) School supervision activities refer to education policies whether education policies issued by the Ministry of National Education (Depdikas) at the central level or the local Education Agency (district / city).
- 3) The supervisory activity program includes priority guidance with its achievement targets in the short term (semester), medium term (one year), and long term (three to years). A set of short-term priorities is established on the basis of the problems / problems faced by each target school. The diversity of problems faced will differentiate the priority targets of supervision in each school.
- 4) The supervisory work program always begins with an assessment of the initial conditions of the school relating to educational resources, school work programs, guidance / learning processes, and student learning / guidance outcomes. In the next stage an assessment and guidance is carried out based on the results of the assessment. Monitoring activities in one period (one year) ended with an evaluation of the results of the supervision and preparation of reports that could be used as the basis for the following year's supervision program.

- 5) The implementation of the supervision program is flexible but does not come out of the provisions concerning the assessment, guidance and monitoring of schools. The school supervisor has the authority to determine, work methods, steps and indicators of the success of the supervisory program by taking into account the objective conditions of the school concerned.

The indicators for managing Madrasah supervisors include: a) Annual program preparation consisting of 2 (two) semester programs, b) Preparation of semester supervision programs at each target school, c) Supervisors prepare the required instruments in accordance with the material / aspects / focus of the problem to be supervised, d) Carry out teacher and / or school principal coaching, e) Monitor the implementation of eight national education standards, f) Carry out a performance assessment of the teacher and / or the principal, g) Compile and classify data from the results of monitoring and guidance, h) Analyzing data from the results of monitoring and guidance, i) Prepare reports on the results of supervision in accordance with the stipulated system, j) Submitting semester and annual reports to the Provincial Ministry of Religion Office or the District / City Ministry of Religion Office, as well as the madrasahs they have built.

2.2. Supervisor Model

2.2.1. Conventional Model

In this model, authoritarian power will influence supervisory behavior, usually visible supervisory behavior is to find fault and find fault. The oversight behavior of this model is to carry out inspections to find fault and find fault. Sometimes it is spying. This behavior by Oliva P.F. called snoopervision (spying). Often called corrective supervision. The practice of finding fault and suppressing these subordinates still exists today. The supervisors came to the school and asked where the RPP was. He said this was wrong and it was wrong. This kind of supervision practice is a way of providing conventional supervision. Not that a supervisor cannot show mistakes. However, the problem is how we communicate what is meant so the teachers realize that what has been done is wrong and must be corrected. If given a good understanding of teacher errors, the teacher will happily correct them without the language of rejection.

2.2.2. Scientific Model

This model has the following characteristics: (1). Implemented in a planned and continuous manner, (2) Systematic and using certain procedures and techniques, (3) Using data collection instruments, and (4) There are objective data obtained from real conditions.

By using meting ratings, rating scales or checklists, students or students assess the process of teaching / teaching activities in the classroom. The results of the study were given to the teacher as a response to the teacher's teaching performance in the past semester. This data does not speak to teachers and teachers who make improvements. The use of this data recorder is closely related to research. However, this is not yet a guarantee for more humane supervision.

2.2.3. Clinical Model

The clinical supervision model is focused on improving the learning process using systematic cycles. Clinical supervision is the process of helping teachers minimize the gap between real teaching behavior and ideal teaching behavior. The clinical supervision model is a coaching process in education that aims to help the professional development of teachers in teaching introduction through objective observation and data analysis, carefully as a basis for efforts to change teacher teaching behavior.

2.2.4. Artistic model

The artistic model has the characteristics of requiring listening attention, requires special expertise to understand one's needs, demands to pay more attention to the class life process that is observed throughout a certain time, and requires a report that shows that the supervisor and teacher supervision dialogue. The supervisor who develops an artistic model will show himself in relations with the teachers who are guided so well that the teachers feel accepted.

2.3. Quality of Madrasah Aliyah

Quality Madrasah are very closely related to the involvement of the community in totality in it. Quality requires a commitment to customer satisfaction that allows improvements to employees, students in doing their jobs as well as possible. Charles Hoy formulated the quality of education is an evaluation of the educational process that increases the need to achieve and develop student talents in a process, and at the same time meets the standards of accountability set by the client who finances the process or output of the education process. According to Hoy and Miskel, quality schools / madrassas are effective schools / Madrasah, which consist of an input, process, and output order.

Quality of Madrasah Aliyah is an advantage possessed by Madrasah Aliyah produced through well-planned educational processes. Madrasah Aliyah quality indicators include: 1) The existence of inputs, processes, and outputs contained in the Madrasah. Quality of a Madrasah can be seen from activities carried out by Madrasah Aliyah supervisors that are useful for the community both teachers and students. 2) In improving the quality of Madrasah Aliyah must serve customer needs both internally and externally. 3) Involving all components that have an interest directly in improving the quality of Islamic Senior High Schools. 4) The existence of measurements by means of evaluation as a reference in improving the quality management of Madrasah Aliyah. 5) There is a shared commitment to the quality culture. 6) View education of Madrasah Aliyah as a system. 7) There is improvement in the quality of sustainable Madrasah Aliyah.

3. Research Methodology

This study uses a qualitative approach. According to Bogdan and Taylor, as quoted by Moleong, it defines qualitative methods as research procedures that produce descriptive data in the form of written or oral words from people and observable behavior. This approach is directed at the background and the individual holistically. So, in this case it is not permissible to isolate individuals or organizations into variables or hypotheses, but need to view them as part of a whole.

The reason for this study using a qualitative approach is because in this study the resulting data is descriptive data obtained from data in the form of writing, words and documents originating from sources or informants who are studied and can be trusted. The purpose of descriptive research is to make a systematic, factual, and accurate enunciation of the facts and nature of a particular population or area.

The object of this study is the management of supervisors in improving the quality of Madrasah in MAN / MAS Jambi Province. In the study, researchers looked at the activities of supervisors which began from planning, implementation, and evaluation giving supervision to the madrasa. In addition, the researchers met with the Head of Madrasah Education, Head of the Office of the Ministry of Religion, supervisors, heads of MA, Deputy Heads, teachers of Jambi City, Muaro Jambi District, Kerinci Regency and Tanjung Jabung Timur Regency. Associated with this research, the place of the study was carried out at MAN / MAS Ministry of Religion of Jambi City, Ministry of Religion of Muaro Jambi Regency, Ministry of Religion of Tanjung Jabung Timur Regency, Ministry of Religion of Kerinci Regency.

4. Results of Research and Discussion

Management of supervisors in Madrasah Aliyah (MA) has not been carried out optimally. Where the MA supervisor has not made detailed supervision planning based on the time period or work period which consists of: annual supervision planning, semester supervision planning, academic supervision plan, and managerial supervision plan. Furthermore, the supervisor does not supervise the teacher in conducting learning activities in the MA, this is due to the lack of supervisors' ability to understand their duties.

The internal factors that have not been optimal for Islamic Education (PAI) supervisors in improving the quality of education in MA are as follows: 1) Lack of supervisor competency, 2) Low supervisory resources include: lack of readiness of supervisors, supervisory culture, and supervisors of Tata employees Effort, 3) Lack of supervisory motivation, 4) Lack of supervisor's commitment. While the external factors have not been optimal, MA / MAS supervisors in improving the quality of education in MA are as follows: 1) Supervisory recruitment. A supervisor of MAN / MAS Jambi Province who was appointed by the head of the Ministry of Religion of Jambi City, Muaro Jambi District, East Tanjung Jabung Regency and Kerinci Regency was not recruited through a supervisory test. 2) Effect of government policy. This is one of the obstacles, if there is a change of head of the Ministry of Religion, it will automatically change its policies regarding supervisors. 3) Lack of support from the Ministry of Religion. Where the Ministry of Religion does not help supervisors in making their work programs to supervise teachers in teaching activities at the MA.

The efforts of the supervisor of the MA in improving the quality of education are: 1) Enhancing supervisory capabilities. One effort to increase MA supervisors in teacher learning activities at the MA is to improve supervisory capabilities. 2) Supervision of supervisor performance. Monitoring of the performance of supervisors can improve the quality of education in the MA. Supervision of the performance of supervisors through supervisory education and training, seminars, workshops, supervisory working groups and certification supervisors. 3) Support from the Ministry of

Religion. With the support of the Ministry of Religion for supervisors to supervise teachers to teach in the classroom such as providing funds and motorbike transportation to effectively monitor activities in conducting supervision to improve the quality of Madrasah.

The supervisory model of conducting supervisors includes conventional models, scientific models, clinical models and artistic models having their respective characteristics, therefore the use of supervisory models in the implementation of supervisory duties must be appropriate, so that the implementation of supervision can take place effectively and efficiently. According to researchers, the appropriate scientific and clinical collaborative supervisor model is used by supervisors in the implementation of supervisory duties to improve the quality of Madrasah, because the scientific model is a supervisor model used to collect data or information and assess the performance of principals and teachers. While the clinical model is a form of supervision that is focused on improving learning through systematic cycles, in planning intensive and careful observations and analyzes of the appearance of real teaching, and aims to make changes in a rational way.

5. Conclusion

Management is essentially a process of planning, organizing, implementing, leading and controlling the business of the members of the organization and utilizing all organizational resources in order to achieve the stated goals. The activity of a job is not carried out by one person, without involving other people. In involving many people in order to achieve the goals of a leader must be able to professionally manage the organization so that the intended objectives can be achieved properly. Memenage or managing Madrasah means arranging for all madrasa potential to function optimally in supporting the achievement of madrasah goals.

Management of supervisors in Madrasah Aliyah (MA) has not been carried out optimally. Where the MA supervisor has not made detailed supervision planning based on the time period or work period consisting of: annual supervision planning, semester supervision planning, academic supervision plan, and managerial supervision plan. Besides that supervisors do not supervise teachers in conducting learning activities in the MA, this is due to the fact that supervisors who are recruited or appointed are not conducted by the supervisor test.

The supervisor model consists of traditional, scientific, clinical, and artistic models. However, in the future the madrasah supervisor blog model needs to be applied in teacher training in the Jambi Province MA. The model has two main parts, namely the format of the blog page design and the content of the coaching material. The design of the madrasah supervisor blog model that bases on the needs of teacher coaching materials, is proven to be effective can be applied by madrasah supervisors as a media for teacher development, with the following characteristics: madrasah supervisors upload teacher development material, assisted teachers access it. With the appropriateness of the material to the needs of teacher training, the model can really improve the professional abilities of teachers so that they can improve the quality of the madrasa.

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